

Leadership Styles of School Principals and Their Reflections in Practice

Okul Müdürlerinin Liderlik Stilleri ve Uygulamadaki Yansımaları

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ÖZET

Bu araştırmanın amacı, Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı'na bağlı okul müdürlerinin liderlik stilleri ve uygulamadaki yansımaları ile ilgili düşünceleri anlaşılmasına çalışılmasıdır. Araştırmada 42 öğretmen ve 10 okul müdüründen araştırmacı tarafından oluşturulan 10 soru ile veri toplanmıştır. Katılımcıların verdikleri cevaplar incelendiğinde öğretmenlerin okul yöneticilerinin şu özellikleri taşıması gerektiğini belirtmişlerdir: Kurumda çalışan herkesi vizyonuna inandırabilmeli ve ekip olarak planlamalar yapabilmelidir. Okul yöneticileri iletişim ve ikna yeteneğine sahip bir yönetici olmalıdır, dinlemesini bilen, çalışma arkadaşlarını iyi taniyan, sorunlarına akılcı ve hızlı çözümler bulmalıdır. Yaptığı işlerde kendine güvenmeli ve ekip arkadaşlarına da bu güveni aşılamalıdır. Okul yöneticisi güven verebilmek için dürüst ve adil olmalı, sağlam bir kişiliğe sahip olmalıdır. Emir veren değil öğretmeniyle beraber çalışan bir yönetici olmalıdır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Liderlik, Okul Müdürü, Öğretmen.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to understand the thoughts of school principals affiliated with the Ministry of National Education regarding their leadership styles and their reflections in practice. Data was collected from 42 teachers and 10 school principals using 10 questions developed by the researcher. When the answers given by the participants were examined, it was stated that teachers stated that school principals should have the following characteristics: They should be able to convince everyone working in the institution of their vision and make plans as a team. School principals should be managers with communication and persuasion skills, know how to listen, know their colleagues well, and find rational and fast solutions to their problems. They should be confident in their work and instill this confidence in their teammates. To inspire trust, a school principal should be honest and fair and have a strong personality. They should be a manager who works with their teachers, not a manager who gives orders.

Keywords: Leadership, School Principal, Teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Humans are social beings. People living together must cooperate to meet their own needs and achieve goals that they cannot achieve alone. People who come together to achieve the same goal always need leaders to manage and guide them. There are leaders wherever there is a human community. The emergence of leadership is as old as human history. People need other people to continue their daily lives. To achieve goals, to be successful, effective and efficient, it is necessary to share the work among themselves. A leader is needed who will ensure this cooperation and make the followers work with pleasure towards a goal (Ceylan,1997:314).

“A School is as Much a School as Its Principal”

One of the common characteristics of all schools is that the leadership of the school principal shapes the school. The saying “A school is as much a school as its principal” shows that this is a general opinion accepted by everyone. The impression I have gained from the colleague interviews and studies conducted with school leaders, especially in recent years, is that principals in our country do not create much influence and action in other leadership areas where they can make a real difference by focusing on the logistics problems of their schools.

The changes in the curricula, systems and the principals who manage the schools and the leadership styles exhibited by the principals affect the school culture levels of the teachers working in the

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institutions. The traditionally defined leadership approach is defined as the whole of the characteristics related to having the necessary qualifications, skills and experience to gather a certain group of people around certain goals and to mobilize them to achieve these goals. However, today, leadership is not limited to the processes of influencing people and activating structure. The knowledge, skill and talent levels of humanity today, the way they understand and perceive management, and the tendency to see success as a requirement have made the leader no longer the "person who creates ideas" and the follower the "person who does the job". In today's societies, where competition has intensified and even become destructive, where the morale and satisfaction of employees are reflected in organizational efficiency and effectiveness, and where benefiting from the knowledge, skills and talents that humanity possesses is the most valuable resource, the existence and function of the leader have become much more complex than the simple leader-follower relationship of the past (Bayrak, 1997: 356).

The purpose of this research is to understand the thoughts of school principals affiliated to the Ministry of National Education regarding leadership styles and their reflections in practice. In the field of educational administration, which has started to develop as a separate field in developed countries since the 1950s, many studies have been conducted on leadership from the past to the present and the leadership of educational administrators in this context (Şişman, 2004). Leadership has a special importance for educational organizations. Because educational organizations and leaders are people with important duties and responsibilities in raising generations that will ensure the development and progress of the country. For this reason, it is very important for educational organizations to select and train leaders in a way that will meet the requirements of the information age. The fact that educational administration is given such importance is also understood from the fact that it is the subject of many studies. Studies have been conducted, and suggestions have been made in terms of all dimensions of management. The concept of manager in education has been abandoned and the concept of "Educational Leader" has now begun to be used. Only educational leaders can manage teachers, parents and students who will keep up with the constantly developing and renewed educational conditions. Especially considering that teachers are their greatest supporters in their work, it is of great importance for them to lead them. In our management approach, our educational institutions are primarily entrusted to school principals. Since teachers are the greatest supporters of the administrators who receive this trust, it is primarily the behaviors of the school principal that will increase or decrease their performance. In our research, we have tried to reveal the level of impact of the leadership behaviors of school principals on the job performance of teachers.

Definition of Leadership

Various definitions have been made in many studies conducted on leaders and leadership to date. Some of the definitions are as follows; According to Certo, leadership is defined as the process of directing people's behaviors towards the achievement of certain goals, while according to Hellriegel and Slocum, leadership is defined as the ability to influence, motivate and direct other elements of the organization in order to achieve targeted goals. According to George and Junes, a leader is a person who influences members of groups and organizations in order to ensure that groups and organizations achieve their goals. Krausz defines leadership as a form of power used to influence the activities of other people (Arıkan, 2001: 285). At a time when many people were talking about management, Freud's nephew Peter F. Drucker first addressed the subject of leadership in 1946 in his book "The Concept of the Corporation" (Önen, 2006). Leadership is the ability of a group to; It can be described as an influencing process that encourages people to voluntarily strive to achieve organizational goals, transfers experiences that help achieve common goals, and ensures that they are pleased with the type of leadership applied (Werner, 1993: 17; Cited: Alkın, 2006). Although the word leadership entered world literature in the 14th century, it has been used frequently in the last two centuries. Researchers have defined leadership according to their personal perspectives and the facts they attach importance to. Many definitions have begun to be made with leadership research that began to intensify in the 1950s. Some of these definitions can be listed as follows (Zel, 2001: 90-91; Cited: Güllü, 2009)

- ✓ Leadership is a process of interaction between people directed to achieve predetermined goals in an environment where the communication process takes place.

- ✓ Leadership is to activate the structure with mutual behavior and consensus and to continue this movement.
- ✓ Leadership is a role that adapts those who strive to achieve their goals according to the situation and answers their questions.
- ✓ Leadership is an excess that emerges in terms of effect beyond the mechanical coordination with the daily orders of the organization.
- ✓ Leadership is the activity of influencing human behavior in an organized group in order to fulfill a certain purpose.

It is possible to multiply these definitions. However, as can be seen, the points where the definitions meet are generally the same. The criteria in the common denominator are having a certain purpose, having a certain group of people and having a leader who can direct this group. In this direction, leadership can be defined as the sum of the knowledge and skills to gather a group of people around certain purposes and to mobilize and influence them to achieve these purposes (Zel, 2001: 91; Cited: Güllü, 2009). Therefore, formal organizations are not necessary for the formation of leadership. The second point is that it is not necessary for the leader to be equipped with official authorities for the formation of leadership. The third point is that the leader and the manager are not synonymous. The fourth point is that leadership should not be thought of as a process specific to those who occupy the upper levels of organizations (Koçel, 2001: 466).

Characteristics of a Leader

The definition of leadership, the concept of leadership and the differences between the concepts of leadership and management are summarized in the above sections based on the research conducted. The research conducted on the characteristics of the leader can be summarized as follows:

- ✓ While leaders help shape the culture, culture also helps shape individuals (Akıncı, 1998:78).
- ✓ Leaders are respectful and sensitive to cultural, ethnic and gender differences among employees (Özden, 2002:98).
- ✓ Leaders are people with a balanced and consistent personality structure and the ability to control their emotions and enthusiasm (Aydın, 1997:86).
- ✓ Leaders unite, persuade, inspire, excite, mobilize, create change and leave a mark.

In terms of personality psychology, there are four basic characteristics that form the personality of a leader and cannot be acquired later. These characteristics, together with the innate qualities, form the personality developed in the first twenty years of life. These are having a vision, honesty, professional competence and determination (Baltaş, 2004:34).

School Principal and Leadership in School Management

School principals are people who manage educational institutions. Among the administrators who manage primary schools are the school principal, the assistant principal and the assistant principal. The school principal is the highest authority in the school. The school principal is the one who will realize the goals of the school, keep its structure alive, protect its atmosphere and develop its qualities (Ünal 1991:1).

Educational management is the process of using material and human resources to ensure the desired behavioral change in human behavior; the person who manages this process is the education manager, that is, the school principal (Çelik, 2000: 28-29). According to Taymaz, the education manager, that is, the school principal; is the person who implements and manages the policies and decisions determined within the framework of the special purposes of the educational organization, in accordance with the general purposes and principles of education, provided that the human and material resources are used effectively in order to achieve the determined goals of the educational organizations (Taymaz, 1995:15).

In Türkiye, school principals are equipped with formal authorities because they are appointed (Korkmaz, 1996:30). The school principal is a formal educational leader. The school principal has the leadership powers of legal power, reward power and coercive power together (Çelik, 2000:6). The school principal

is affected by the bureaucratic environment in which he/she is located with his/her leadership qualities. In other words, he/she differs from the leaders in other organizations. To explain this, first, the school principal is the chief or head of the leader. Although it is very difficult to move from the chief image to the leadership image, it can be achieved in some ways. The first of these is to adopt the basic values and ideals of the educational enterprise and to be able to translate them into behavior. These ideals, such as the value of the individual, the importance of cooperation, the efficiency of the school and the development of the student, in a way determine the leadership duties of the school principal. The second is to be an organizer and manager enough to balance the goals of the school with the needs of its members. The third is to be able to create an atmosphere in the school where harmonious human relations are established and function. If one remembers that leadership is a group action and that being a superior only covers personal rights and duties, the school administrator can work towards his group rather than his superior and at least approach their leadership image (Bursalioğlu, 1971).

A school administrator who wants to develop his school in line with its goals must be a leader to provide effective management. With the contemporary management approach, the leadership role of the education administrator has gained importance. If the administrator wants to be effective, he must act as the leader of the group (Kaya, 1991:139).

METHOD

As a method in our research, literature review and the interview form developed by the researcher will be directed to determine the opinions of administrators and teachers regarding the leadership styles of school principals and their reflections in practice. The interview form developed by the researcher consists of two parts. Attention was paid to the open-ended questions in the interview form and to ensure that they were easy to understand by the participants. Personal information was included in the first part, and 10 open-ended questions were included in the second part regarding the characteristics that leading administrators should have. The answers given in the interview form applied to school principals and administrators working in 10 randomly selected public schools considering the ease of transportation were carefully examined, the data obtained from the research of the sources written on this subject and the interview form results were compared. The themes used in the analysis process were determined as "leadership styles and their reflections in practice". It was tried to understand the thoughts of teachers and administrators regarding this theme. In the research, face-to-face interviews were conducted with school administrators by the researcher. Prior information was given to the administrators who would be interviewed before the interview, and an appointment was made for the interview. The interviews were distributed to the participants in the schools and obtained in writing from the participants. The data were grouped under the determined themes by coding by the researcher.

The universe of the project consists of 4640 teachers and administrators working in public schools affiliated to the Pendik District National Education Directorate. The sample of the research consists of a total of 52 principals and teachers (10 school principals, 42 teachers) in 10 public schools (primary school, secondary school and high school) affiliated to the Pendik District National Education Directorate.

Findings and Interpretations

The demographic variables of the participants whose opinions were taken in the study were examined, the data were created by taking the percentages and frequencies of their responses to the questions, and the obtained data were interpreted. Analysis of the Responses to the Questions Asked in the Interview Form In the study, face-to-face interviews were conducted with 10 administrators and 42 teachers. During the interview, attention was paid to the explanation and interpretation of the opinions with high frequencies in the study from the findings obtained from the responses given by the administrators and teachers to the questions directed at them.

Table 1: Descriptive Values for the Responses Given by Teachers to the Interview Form Questions (N=42)

Questions	Positive	Negative
1- Our school principal has a vision. He sets goals and does the necessary work to achieve them.	27 (%64,3)	15 (35,7)
2- He always listens to our teachers' problems and helps us solve them.	23 (%54,8)	19 (%45,2)
3- Our school principal gives us confidence in our work.	28 (%66,7)	14 (%33,3)
4- His professional knowledge is sufficient.	31 (%73,8)	11 (%26,2)
5- He acts decisively in his work.	22 (%52,4)	20 (%47,6)
6- The decisions he makes are fair. He treats everyone equally.	18 (%42,8)	24 (%57,2)
7- Uses "we" language, not "I" language in work.	33 (%78,6)	9 (%21,4)
8- Has full confidence in the work he does.	28 (%66,7)	14 (%33,3)
9- Produces fast and effective solutions to events thanks to his reasoning skills.	20 (%47,6)	22 (%52,4)
10- Gives importance to the rights of employees.	33 (%78,6)	9 (%21,4)

As seen in the chart, 27 (64.3%) of the teachers stated that they positively agreed with the question “Our school principal is a visionary. He/she sets the goals and does the necessary work to achieve the goals” regarding the leadership styles of school principals. Of the teachers who filled out the interview form, 23 (54.8%) of the teachers who were asked the question “Our teachers always listen to us about our problems and help us solve the problems” regarding the leadership styles of school principals were positively agreed with. As seen in the chart, 28 (66.7%) of the teachers stated that they positively agreed with the question “Our school principal gives us confidence in our work” regarding the leadership styles of school principals. As seen in the chart, 31 (78.6%) of the teachers stated that they positively agreed with the question “His/her professional knowledge is sufficient” regarding the leadership styles of school principals. As can be seen in the chart, 22 (%52.4) of the teachers indicated that they positively agreed with the question “He acts decisively in his work” regarding the leadership styles of school principals. As can be seen in the chart, 24 (%57.2) of the teachers indicated that they negatively agreed with the question “The decisions he makes are fair. He treats everyone equally.” As can be seen in the chart, 33 (%78.6) of the teachers indicated that they positively agreed with the question “He uses “we” language, not “I” language, in his work. As can be seen in the chart, 28 (%66.7) of the teachers indicated that they positively agreed with the question “He has full confidence in his work.” regarding the leadership styles of school principals. As can be seen in the chart, 28 (%66.7) of the teachers indicated that they positively agreed with the question “He produces fast and effective solutions to events thanks to his reasoning ability.” regarding the leadership styles of school principals. 22 (52.4%) of the teachers responded negatively to the question "Does the school principal care about its leadership style?" and 33 (78.6%) of them responded positively to the question "Does the school principal care about its leadership style?" as seen in the chart.

Table 2: Descriptive Values for Responses Given by School Administrators to Interview Form Questions (N=10)

Questions	Positive	Negative
1- I have a vision. I set goals and do the necessary work to achieve them.	10 (% 100)	0
2- I am interested in my teachers' problems; I always listen to them and help them solve their problems.	8 (%80)	2 (%20)
3- I give my teachers confidence in their work.	9 (%90)	1 (%10)
4- My professional knowledge is sufficient.	8 (%80)	2 (%20)
5- I act decisively in my work.	9 (%90)	1 (%10)
6- The decisions I make are fair. I treat everyone equally.	10 (%100)	0
7- I use "we" language, not "I" language in my work.	9 (%90)	1 (%10)
8- I have full confidence in my work.	10 (%100)	0
9- Thanks to my reasoning ability, I produce fast and effective solutions to events.	9 (%90)	1 (%10)
10- I value the rights of employees.	10 (%100)	0

As seen in the chart, school principals stated that they agreed with the question “I have a vision. I set goals and do the necessary work to achieve the goal” regarding their leadership styles with 10% (100%). School principals who filled out the interview form stated that they agreed with the question “I am interested in my teachers’ problems, I always listen to them and help them solve their problems” regarding their leadership styles with 8% (80%) of them. As seen in the chart, school principals stated that they agreed with the question “I give my teachers confidence in their work” regarding their leadership styles with 9% (90%) of them. As seen in the chart, school principals stated that they agreed with the question “My professional knowledge is sufficient” regarding their leadership styles with 8% (80%) of them. As seen in the chart, school principals stated that they agreed with the question “I act decisively in my work” regarding their leadership styles with 8% (80%) of them. 9 (%90) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively to the question “The decisions I make are fair. I treat everyone equally.” regarding their leadership styles. As can be seen in the chart, 9 (%90) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively to the question “I use “we” language, not “I” language in their work.” regarding their leadership styles. As can be seen in the chart, 9 (%100) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively to the question “I have full confidence in the work I do.” regarding their leadership styles. As can be seen in the chart, 9 (%90) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively to the question “Thanks to my reasoning ability, I produce fast and effective solutions to events.” regarding their leadership styles. As can be seen in the chart, 9 (%90) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively to the question “Thanks to my reasoning ability, I produce fast and effective solutions to events.” regarding their leadership styles. As can be seen in the chart, 9 (%90) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively to the question “I care about the rights of the employees.” regarding their leadership styles. All responses (100%) to the question indicate that they agree positively.

CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The information obtained because of the literature review was evaluated in the interview form regarding the leadership characteristics of school principals and teachers working in primary and secondary schools in Pendik district in the 2023-2024 academic year and the following findings were obtained.

The sample group consists of 52 teachers, 27 (51.9%) of whom are female and 25 (48.1) of whom are male. It is seen that 12 (23.1%) of the teachers constituting the sample group have 1-10 years of service, 29 (55.8%) have 11-20 years of service, and 11 (21.1%) have 21 years or more. It is seen that 10 (19.2) of the teachers constituting the sample group are school principals and 42 (80%) are teachers. It is seen that 5 (9.6%) of the teachers constituting the sample group are between 20-30 years old, 36 (69.2%) are between 31-40 years old, and 11 (21.1%) are over 41 years old.

Results of Teachers' Questions on Leadership Styles

As seen in the chart, 27 of the teachers (64.3%) stated that they agreed positively with the question "Our school principal is a visionary. He sets the goals and does the necessary work to achieve the goal" regarding the leadership styles of school principals. School principals should be able to convince everyone working in the institution of their vision and make plans as a team. School principals should be managers with communication and persuasion skills. Bayrak (2001) found that in the visionary leadership dimension, an average of 70% of administrators stated that they had visionary leadership skills; an average of 60% of classroom and branch teachers found school administrators sufficient in terms of visionary leadership skills. According to Acar (2006)'s research, administrators' visionary leadership skills are at a low level compared to teachers' perceptions.

When the teachers who filled out the interview form were asked the question "Teachers always listen to us about our problems and help us solve problems" regarding the leadership styles of school administrators, 23 of the teachers' perceptions (54.8%) were positive. School administrators should know how to listen, know their colleagues well, and find rational and fast solutions to their problems. According to Gürses' (2006) research, administrators are expected to establish verbal communication with all employees, be calm and determined while talking, try to find solutions to problems, give feedback to the people they communicate with, evaluate and interpret the feedback they receive, and make necessary corrections. As seen in the chart In the question "Our school principal gives us confidence in our work" regarding the leadership styles of school principals, 28 (66.7%) of the teachers stated that they agreed positively. Cemaloğlu (2002) stated that the cooperation of school principals with teachers, their opportunities for self-development and their efforts to create a positive school climate significantly contributed to the performance of teachers. As can be seen in the table, in the question "His professional knowledge is sufficient" regarding the leadership qualities of school principals, 31 (78.6%) of the teachers stated that they agreed positively. The leader should gain the belief of the employees in him/her. The employees around him/her become more successful and make an effort by loving the job and the leader. The leader achieves success together with the team. As can be seen in the table, in the question "He/she acts decisively in the work he/she does" regarding the leadership styles of school principals, teachers stated that they agreed positively. 22 (52.4%) of the answers to the question indicate that they agree positively. The leader must have strong intuition. He must be confident in his work and must create this confidence in his teammates.

As can be seen in the chart, 24 (%57.2) of the teachers' responses to the question "The decisions they make are fair. They treat everyone equally" regarding the leadership styles of school principals indicate that they agree negatively. Erkuş (1997), in his research which includes the leadership dimensions of school principals such as establishing the structure and showing understanding, has revealed that teachers generally do not agree with the leadership perceptions of school principals. In addition, in the studies conducted by Alıç (1985) and Güler (1987), significant differences were found between the opinions of teachers and administrators regarding leadership perceptions. In order to inspire trust, a school principal must be honest and fair and have a strong personality. If teachers state that they are in an environment of inequality and injustice, this brings failure. Our school principals, who state that justice is one of the most important values, state that the employees of the institution must be treated fairly for the success of the staff. In the research of Gezici (2007), who exhibited democratic leadership behavior; It has been observed that employees have higher satisfaction levels when they work with a manager who is fair, open to suggestions, makes decisions together with his employees, pays satisfactory wages and sees his employees as human beings. As can be seen in the chart, 33 (78.6%) of the teachers' responses to the question "He uses a "we" language in his work, not an "I" language in his work" regarding the leadership styles of school principals indicate that they agree positively. School principals need to have well-developed communication and persuasion skills. It is also seen that teachers have a positive perception in this direction. In Gezici's (2007) research, it has been observed that the autocratic leadership behavior, especially used in private educational institutions, is not adopted by the employees and the satisfaction levels of the employees with their work are quite low. The leader manager should be a manager who works together with the teacher, not one who gives orders. It can be said that leader managers who use a "we" language, not an "I" language in their work are more successful in taking the staff to the target. As can be seen in the chart, 28 (66.7%) of the teachers' responses to the question "He

has full confidence in the work he does" regarding the leadership styles of school principals indicate that they agree positively. As seen in the chart, 22 (52.4%) of the teachers' responses to the question "He/she produces fast and effective solutions to events thanks to his/her reasoning skills" regarding the leadership styles of school principals indicate that they agree negatively. It is possible for school principals to display leadership behaviors by being trained in this area. Çakar and Arbak (2003) stated in their research that managers with high emotional intelligence can be more of a source of inspiration for employees and that followers act according to the emotional cues he/she gives directly or indirectly. As seen in the chart, 33 (78.6%) of the teachers' responses to the question "He/she cares about the rights of employees" regarding the leadership styles of school principals indicate that they agree positively. The manager's power of influence increases his/her effectiveness and efficiency.

Result of School Administrators' Responses to Questions About Leadership Styles

As seen in the chart, school administrators stated that they all agreed with the question "I have a vision. I set goals and do the necessary work to achieve the goal" with 10% (100%) in the positive direction regarding their leadership styles. Razi (2003) stated that administrators perceive themselves as highly competent, but teachers perceive administrators as incompetent. It is seen that there are some differences in perceptions between administrators' perceptions of themselves and teachers' perceptions of administrators in terms of leadership styles.

The school principals who filled out the interview form, were asked the question "I am interested in my teachers' problems, I always listen to them and help them solve their problems" regarding their leadership styles, and 8 (80%) of them stated a positive opinion. It can be thought that school principals who are sensitive to the needs and expectations of their employees will create a more positive work environment. As can be seen in the chart, 9 (90%) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively with the question "I give my teachers confidence in their work" regarding their leadership styles. The fact that school principals do not intervene too much, make teachers feel that they support their work and appreciate their work positively affects teachers and increases success. As can be seen in the chart, 8 (80%) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively with the question "My professional knowledge is sufficient" regarding their leadership styles. A leader is someone who is ready to learn throughout their life and is open to new ideas and the opinions of their friends. As seen in the chart, 9 (90%) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively with the question "I act decisively in my work" regarding their leadership characteristics. Decision making is the most important responsibility of the principal. Decision making is not enough, the given decision must also be implemented and followed up. As seen in the chart, all 10 (100%) of the school principals stated that they agreed positively with the question "I make decisions are fair. I treat everyone equally" regarding their leadership styles. The principals think that they demonstrate leadership characteristics, but the teachers state that they do not see these behaviors in their principals or that they rarely see them. Usdan, (2000) states that school principals are the most important elements in the education system, but when their selection, training, assignment, in-service training situations and workloads are taken into consideration, it is evaluated that they cannot adequately fulfill many of the roles presented in this study. As seen in the chart, the school principals stated that they "use the 'we' language in their work, not the 'I' language" regarding their leadership styles. It can be said that giving importance to teachers' opinions and their participation in decisions will increase teachers' motivation. As can be seen in the table, all of the teachers (100%) positively agree with the question "I have full confidence in my work." regarding their leadership styles. Çalık and Şehitoğlu (2006), in their study titled "School Principals' Competencies to Fulfill Human Resources Management Functions," stated that school principals generally act in accordance with the legislation in their practices, take teachers' professional competencies into consideration, but are inadequate in involving teachers in decisions taken and in giving rewards or punishments, which is an incentive behavior, according to objective criteria. As can be seen in the table, school principals 9 of the students (90%) positively agree with the question "Thanks to my reasoning ability, I produce fast and effective solutions to events." regarding their leadership styles. As seen in the chart, school principals indicate that they agree positively with all responses (100%) to the question "I care about the rights of employees" regarding their leadership styles.

Suggestions

- ✓ School principalship should not be an additional duty but a professional one.
- ✓ In-service training studies should be planned on effective communication.
- ✓ Seminar studies should be conducted to develop school principals.
- ✓ School principals should not be appointed with just an exam. The candidates determined because of the exam should be trained in cooperation with universities and then their appointment should be made.
- ✓ School principals should not be removed from their duties with simple administrative measures.
- ✓ They should start their duties as trainee principals, and the principal candidates who are successful within the specified periods should be appointed within certain years.
- ✓ There should be rotation, and the current 5-year process for principal appointments should continue.

Principals should be transparent in management and ensure that those who are managed can easily reach higher authorities when necessary.

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